

Efference Copy Signals Enhance Haptic Precision During Active Information Acquisition

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Abstract. Haptic perception arises from the integration of cutaneous and kinesthetic inputs (proprioceptive and efference copy signals), but the specific contributions of these signals remain debated. To dissociate their roles, we conducted a spatial frequency discrimination experiment with three conditions: active (free arm movement), passive-arm (motor-driven replay of active kinematics), and passive-stimulus (stationary arm with probe motion matched to active kinematics). We found lower just noticeable differences in the active condition relative to both passive conditions, with no difference between passive conditions, suggesting that the prediction of arm movement from the efference copy enhances perceptual precision during active sensing.

Keywords: efference copy · proprioception · cutaneous

1 Introduction

Haptic perception arises from the integration of cutaneous and kinesthetic inputs [1]. Cutaneous signals are conveyed by mechanoreceptors in the skin [2], whereas kinesthetic input comprises proprioceptive cues encoding body position [3] and efference copy signals that predict the sensory consequences of motor commands [4]. The contribution of these inputs depends on the observer’s control over movement. During active exploration, cutaneous, proprioceptive, and efference copy signals are all available (active haptic perception). In the absence of voluntary movement, perception is either tactile, relying solely on cutaneous input, or passive haptic, which additionally involves proprioceptive information from externally driven movement [1].

It is clear that efference copies play a role for the attenuation of irrelevant tactile stimuli in motor tasks [5, 6], and that they can improve the perception of own movements, e.g. limb position [7]. It is less clear whether efference copies are used in the haptic perception of environmental properties. Active haptic perception can enhance perceptual precision relative to tactile conditions, suggesting that signals on limb movement support perception [8, 9], but it is unclear in

how far these effects arise from efference-copy based predictions or proprioceptive sensing. Here, we disentangled the contributions of different informational sources in a spatial discrimination task, where knowledge on limb velocity is crucial for the judgment. We hypothesized that perceptual precision would be highest in active perception, where cutaneous, proprioceptive and efference-copy based information are available; intermediate in an passive-arm condition, where only cutaneous and proprioceptive information are present because the arm was moved by a device; and lowest in a passive-stimulus condition, where only cutaneous information is available from moving the stimulus below the finger.

2 Method

10 participants (6 females, 4 males; age range: 19-33 years with mean age of 25.1, $SD = 4.38$) participated in the experiment. They provided written informed consent prior to participation.

There were three conditions: (1) active exploration, in which participants freely moved their arm to explore the stimulus; (2) passive-arm movement, in which participants' kinematics were yoked and their arm was moved by a motor-controlled device; and (3) passive-stimulus movement, in which the arm remained stationary while the stimulus probe moved with matched kinematics. The order of the passive conditions was counterbalanced across participants.

Participants sat in front of a custom-built setup (Fig. 1A) comprising two motors (one controlling the arm rest - one controlling the stimulus probe; item model SE 60-150-3-60-AK) and two linear units allowing either free arm movement without motor intervention or motor-guided movement (item model KLE 6 60×60 LR). Position data were recorded using position sensor (Waycon-LAS2TM 500) and was used to calculate movement kinematics to use in passive conditions. Participants performed a spatial discrimination task using oriented textures with a constant ridge width of 0.5 mm and varying inter-element distances. The method of constant stimuli was used with two reference spacings (15.3-16.3 mm) and comparison ranges of 11.3–19.3 mm and 12.3–20.3 mm, respectively, in 1.0 mm steps (9 repetitions per pair). The reference stimulus was presented visually, the comparison tactually. Participants' view of their arm was occluded. Each trial began with a 5s presentation of the reference, followed by tactile exploration consisting of 4 strokes of different length, each cued by an auditory signal. Participants then indicated which stimulus had the higher spatial frequency.

3 Results

Just noticeable differences (JNDs) were derived from the 75% and 25% thresholds of a Gaussian-fitted psychometric function applied to binomial data using a Bayesian fitting method [10]. Planned t-tests were conducted to test a priori hypotheses. JNDs were significantly lower in the active condition ($M = 1.33$) than in the passive-stimulus condition ($M = 1.81$), $t(8) = -1.880$, $p = .048$, and with a trend toward lower values compared to the passive-arm condition ($M =$

1.72), $t(8) = -1.779$, $p = .055$ (Fig. 1B). No significant differences were observed between the passive conditions.

4 Discussion

These results show that active touch provides a perceptual advantage over passive touch in line with [8, 9] and, more importantly, highlight the role of efference copy-based predictions in haptic perception, by showing this advantage when cutaneous and proprioceptive information is kept constant. Moreover, our findings extend previous work by suggesting that efference copies do not interfere with task-relevant signals during information acquisition, whereas they suppress task-irrelevant inputs in motor actions [5, 6]. They also showed that efference copy enhances perception when limb-related information is relevant for the perceptual judgment (e.g., limb velocity for inferring spatial frequency from temporal element sequences), whereas studies on curvature perception did not find such an effect [11], suggesting possible task-dependent contributions of efference copy in haptic perception.

Open Questions Theoretically, how efference copy is used to predict different environmental properties (e.g., shape or texture) remains an open question. Practically, a better understanding of these informational sources may inform the development of neural prosthetics and haptic technologies by clarifying their roles in haptic perception, and may be of interest to researchers in this area.

Fig. 1. A) Depiction of experimental setup. B) JNDs as a function of active, passive-arm, passive stimulus conditions; error bars depict standard errors of the mean.

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Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare no competing interests.

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